

Exploring Factors Influencing Information Utilisation by Hepatitis B and C Patients at Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital, South Africa

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Abstract

Background: This study investigated the factors influencing information utilization by Hepatitis B (HBV) and Hepatitis C (HCV) patients at Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital, South Africa.

Method: Using purposive sampling techniques, in-depth interviews were conducted with HBV and HCV patients. A qualitative approach was adopted to collect data. All relevant ethical procedures were followed, and necessary ethics committee approvals were obtained. Individual patients who consented were interviewed until data saturation was reached at the eighteenth interview. Patients who did not participate were excluded. The qualitative data were coded and analyzed according to themes.

Findings/Results: The findings revealed that the primary factors motivating patients' information use were trust in the information provided, the need to gain health knowledge, and the desire to improve their health condition. Additionally, the belief in the received information and the recognition of health information's importance to their needs were significant motivators.

Conclusion: The study concluded that trust in health knowledge, curiosity about health conditions, the need to increase survival chances, and better treatment are key factors motivating patients' information use. However, many patients remain unclear about the importance and usefulness of health information for their conditions.

Recommendations: The study recommends that policymakers improve health information and communication strategies to effectively reach HBV and HCV patients. Enhancing

patient information, education, health promotion, and awareness is crucial for health improvement.

Keywords: Information utilisation, motivating factors, Hepatitis B and C, Health information, Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital, South Africa

Introduction

Hepatitis B (HBV) and Hepatitis C (HCV) are dangerous diseases prevalent in many developed and developing countries, including Africa and sub-regions (World Health Organization, 2024; Onyekwere *et al.*, 2016). HBV and HCV have affected over 325 million people worldwide. According to WHO (2024), there are different types of hepatitis ranging from A, B, C, D, and E; however, type B and C cause chronic liver cirrhosis, cancer, and viral hepatitis-related deaths in hundreds of millions of people. The study predicted that 4.5 million hepatitis-related deaths can be preventable through vaccination, diagnostic tests, medicines, and education campaigns by 2030, especially in low- and middle-income countries. The prevalence rate of HBV and HCV in African areas varies in percentage due to insufficient and inaccurate data. Appropriate use of information by patients is vital to create awareness and as well provide preventive measures which may likely help to reduce the spread of chronic HBV and HCV diseases in African regions, specifically in South Africa, to achieve the goal of hepatitis eradication by the year 2030 (Rasekh *et al.*, 2019).

Health information utilisation is essential for effectively controlling the spread of deadly diseases, providing solutions, making informed decisions, and achieving meaningful treatment outcomes. The extent of information utilisation depends on the motivating factors. The motivating factors for information use vary depending on patient backgrounds of patients (age, gender, socioeconomic factors, education levels, and cultural beliefs), which may likely influence the decision to use information and perhaps shape their information use behaviour (Houston *et al.*, 2015). Scholars believe that the use of information depends on the potential benefits or usefulness perceived by individuals for avoiding the risks, for the purpose of reducing the spread or effect of certain diseases (Salmanzadeh *et al.*, 2016, p. 380). The beliefs about improving health conditions sometimes influence individual actions to use the information for prevention, treatment, and management; it could be based on patients' experience (Anuar *et al.*, 2020).

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which may likely influence the decision to use information and perhaps shape their information use behaviour (Houston et al., 2015). Much has been written concerning influencing factors responsible for patient information use (Mak *et al.*, 2018, p. 262; Kuecuekbalaban *et al.*, 2017, p. 1; Salmanzadeh *et al.*, 2016, p. 380). Information use could be motivated by different factors but depends on the circumstances and needs of individuals at a particular time (Kuecuekbalaban *et al.*, 2017, p. 1; Salmanzadeh *et al.*, 2016, p. 380). Scholars believe that the use of information depends on the potential benefits or usefulness perceived by individuals for avoiding the risks, for the purpose of reducing the spread or effect of certain diseases (Salmanzadeh *et al.*, 2016, p. 380). The beliefs about improving health conditions sometimes influence individual actions to use the information for prevention, treatment, and management; perhaps it could be based on patients' experience (Anuar et al., 2020).

Patients' experiences have significantly motivated information utilisation in many studies (Byron et al., 2020; Thomas et al., 2016). Patients' experiences with chronic illnesses have been reported in several health information-related studies regarding fear of losing their lives, constant pain and pain management, experiences with stigmatisation, especially from family members and workmates, uncertainty related to their diagnosis, and among others may likely influence the extent of their information-use (Byron et al., 2020; Thomas et al., 2016). Based on the submissions by information behaviour scholars, patients' experiences are part of the antecedent factors that can influence the perception of information users and can also motivate users' information use behaviour (Case & Given, 2016, p. 157; Johnson & Case, 2012;40).

Despite the essential use of health information to save human lives and improve the quality of patients' lives, as highlighted in several studies (Kushniruk et al., 2019; Dijs-Elsinga et al., 2010), the incidence of HBV and HCV is increasing in South Africa, perhaps the effective use of hepatitis-related information is still lacking (Hung *et al.*, 2021; Musa *et al.*, 2015, p. 163). Despite the benefits of information use to effectively help in controlling the spread of HBV and HCV diseases, support patient's adherence to required medication, make informed decisions, and achieve meaningful treatment outcomes in African sub-regions and specifically in a country like South Africa, the rate of spread is increasing (Hsu et al., 2023; Moonsamy et al., 2022; Maepa et al., 2022). It was uncertain what specific factors could influence the effective use of information by patients receiving treatment at Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital, South Africa. Studies exploring the essential understanding of potential factors influencing information use by Hepatitis B and C patients at Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital, South Africa, are limited. This study explores factors motivating hepatitis B and C to seek information, the patient's experiences with

the diseases, the importance of information use, and patients' belief in the usefulness of health-related information.

Statement of Problems

The incidence of hepatitis B and C in Sub-Saharan Africa has been established (WHO, 2024). The incidence left the regions with many constraints (Sonderup et al., 2024). Regional variability of the prevalence was reported in sub-Saharan Africa, which put a severe burden on both patients and their caregivers due to the health implications resulting from acute and chronic liver diseases, hepatic decompensation, and hepatocellular carcinoma (Hung *et al.*, 2021; Musa *et al.*, 2015; Mast *et al.*, 2008; Bosch *et al.*, 2018), the role of information cannot be ignored in the prevention, control and eradication of diseases, adequate care, treatment and health recovery, and health improvement of patients depending on availability and access to Information (WHO, 2024).

Research indicated that the urgent need for practical measures to strengthen the prevention and control measures for viral infection transmission in various regions of Africa is critical (Altinawe et al., 2024), which requires effective methods of information provisions and communication and information utilisation by members of the public. Health information use is essential to enhance patients' health improvement and outcomes and improve the overall quality of patient care (Peyman et al., 2012; Buntin et al., 2011). Findings from health-related studies confirmed that information used by patients depends on various factors related to the demographics and backgrounds of patients regarding socioeconomic factors, education levels, and cultural beliefs) which may influence their health-related decision whether to use information (Houston et al., 2015). On the other hand, studies indicated that knowledge of preventive information is essential as a motivation factor for information use, while other scholars believe that understanding the nature of illnesses is an essential factor that patients must consider before choosing their pattern of information use. Regarding HBV and HCV patients using Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital South Africa, uncertain factors motivated their information use.

Despite the enormous benefits of health information utilisation for prevention and cure and the contributions of patients' experiences in guiding information for preventive purposes and improved health outcomes, knowledge of HBV and HCV-related information needs to be improved among patients using the healthcare facilities at Ngwelezane tertiary hospital. It was unclear if the patients understood the importance of

the benefits and usefulness of health-related information for preventing hepatitis B and C. The researcher was unsure of the motivating factors behind the inadequacy in patients' use of information, either for preventive purposes or otherwise. The reasons behind not using information, especially by patients receiving therapy at the healthcare facility, were yet to be discovered.

Study shows that patients' beliefs in the benefits of health-related information use is an essential motivating factor that can enhance information use by patients, especially health information related to medication adherence, and timely vaccination for preventative purposes to facilitate speedy recovery and elimination of chronic diseases such as HBV and HCV in society. Unfortunately, trust and belief in preventive information use is lacking among patients using the healthcare facilities at Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital, KwaZulu-Natal, to facilitate health improvement (Kew, 1996b, p. 395; Kew et al., G., 1990a:873). This study addresses the need for more literature on factors contributing to the use of Information by HBV and HCV patients at Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital, South Africa. The study focuses on these gaps by identifying factors contributing to the use of Information by HBV and HCV patients at Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital, South Africa.

Research Questions

1. What factors motivated hepatitis B and C to use the information at Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital, South Africa?
2. What are the experiences of hepatitis B and C and the importance of information used on hepatitis B and C for patients at Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital, South Africa,
3. Do hepatitis B and C patients at Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital, South Africa, believe in the usefulness of health-related information?

Methodology

Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital is one of the largest tertiary hospitals in the District of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa (KwaZulu-Natal Department of Health, 2001:1; 2019:1). The hospital falls within the range of tertiary (academic) hospitals in the district of KwaZulu-Natal. The study follows the interpretivism idea of research to investigate factors responsible for HBV and HCV patients' information use through a face-to-face, in-depth interview during their visits to the clinic. The qualitative method in this case study design also allowed the researcher and the research assistant to take unstructured notes about the events and record the interviews from the participants' activities using a mobile phone

at the hospital's hepatitis clinic. The study's target population was the entire HBV and HCV patients who visited the hepatitis clinic for treatment during data collection, who were eighteen years and above, experienced, knowledgeable, and willing to provide rich information of value to the study (Ibinaiye & Jiyane, 2023; Etikan *et al.*, 2016; Tongco, 2007). A purposive sampling technique was used while data was collected through in-depth interviews with patients who consented and availed themselves of the interview. The data collection procedure involved recruiting participants for qualitative data in Ngwelezane District Hospital, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa, between 2020 and 2021. The researchers applied inclusive and exclusive criteria to avoid bias and ensure that only patients suffering from HBV and HCV diseases were recruited for the interview. Data saturation levels were also used to determine the sampling size. The use of data saturation is common in qualitative studies for collecting qualitative data. According to Guest *et al.* (2006, p. 59), data saturation is a point at which no new information is observed in the data (. (Etikan *et al.*, 2016; Tongco, 2007). The qualitative aspect of the data was analysed using thematic analysis.

Despite the challenges with data collection due to COVID-19, all COVID-19 protocols and restrictions were observed with patients before interviews with patients within hospital facilities. The signed informed consent was archived for future reference. At the same time, the confidentiality policy of patient information use was duly followed. Patients were reassured that non-participation in the interview had no consequences because it was voluntary. They were free to withdraw their participation if they wished. Other participants who declined were excluded. The qualitative data were proofread, organised and interpreted according to the theme of the objectives set for the study and related to the study's theoretical framework.

Results

This section presents the data analysis collected through the participants' interviews. The following section presents the participants' biodata for the qualitative data collection. Table 1 illustrates the biodata of the participants for qualitative data collection.

Table 1. The Biodata of the Participants for Qualitative Interview

Participants	Participants		Per	Economic Status		Age Group	
	Gender						
HBV and HCV Patients	Male	Female	3	Employed	Not Employed	20-	1
	8	10				30-	5
						39	
						40-	6
						49	
		50-	6				
		59					
Total	8	10	3	15			18

Table 5.2: Participants for the qualitative interview based on purposive sampling.

Table 1 shows the bio-data of the participants using the interview as a means of data collection from the population group. Most participants were female (n=10; 55.6%), and others were male (n=8; 44.4%). Most participants were not employed (n=15; 83.3%), against a few employed (n=3; 16.7%). On the other hand, the age range of the majority of the participants was between 40 - 49 years (n=12; 66.7%), followed by 30 - 39 (n=5; 28%) and 20 - 29 (n=1; 5.6%). The data collected from HBV and HCV patients were based on *factors responsible for HBV and HCV patients' information use through Ngwelezane Hospital, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa*. The following are the developing themes.

Factors Contributing to the Use of Information by HBV and HCV Patients

Table 2: Factors Contributing to the Use of Information by HBV and HCV Patients

<p>Research Question What factors motivated you to use information on hepatitis B and C?</p>	<p><i>I have trust in the information provided. I am still determining. I want to gain health knowledge. I want to improve my health condition. I believe in the information received. The most important motivating factor is that health information is vital to my health needs.</i></p>
	<p><i>My motivating factor is that I want to gain health knowledge. I was anxious about my state of health. I was curious to know my health condition. Health information is essential to my health needs.</i></p>
	<p><i>My motivating factor is that I want to improve my health condition. I seek health information because I trust that information will help me. I am unsure, but health information is vital to my health needs.</i></p>
	<p><i>I used health information to stay well-informed, to help me get healed, and to evaluate the danger of not getting treated. I only sought information to increase my chances of survival.</i></p>
<p>Based on your experiences of the diseases, how vital is information related to your use of information?</p>	<p><i>Using information is very important for improving my health. Seeking information is very important for me to stay informed and seek better treatment</i></p>
<p>Do you believe in the usefulness of hepatitis B and C-related health information?</p>	<p><i>"I believe health information is useful for my health".</i> <i>"Yes, I believe health information is useful for my health".</i></p>

Discussion of Findings

Based on this study's objectives, findings established a connection between patient information use and contributing factors such as trust, beliefs, and health knowledge and patients' use of health-related information, as revealed in the patients' narrations. In addition, all the patients believed the information was useful to their health. Furthermore, findings revealed that the most important factor that motivated patients' information use on HBV or HCV was the need to increase the chances of survival. Other factors included evaluating dangers, healing expectations, remaining informed, and seeking authenticity of the information. The study indicates that the patients recognised the importance of information and health knowledge derived from hepatitis-related information for survival. Interestingly, all the patients agreed that hepatitis B and C health-related information is helpful, which means that understanding the nature of the disease, protection against different infections, treatment, and social support and care can be possible through effective information use.

Patients were asked, *"What factors motivated you to use information on hepatitis B and C?"*

Most of the patients responded by saying:

I have trust in the information provided. I am still determining. I want to gain health knowledge. I want to improve my health condition. I believe in the information received. The most important motivating factor is that health information is vital to my health needs.

My motivating factor is that I want to gain health knowledge. I was anxious about my state of health. I was curious to know my health condition. Health information is essential to my health needs.

My motivating factor is that I want to improve my health condition. I seek health information because I trust that information will help me. I am unsure, but health information is vital to my health needs.

I used health information to stay well-informed, to help me get healed, and to evaluate the danger of not getting treated. I only sought information to increase my chances of survival.

In response to the question, "*What factors motivated you to use information on hepatitis B and C?*" one participant indicated that they *trusted the information provided by the health professionals*. In contrast, another said: "*I believe in the information received*". Similar findings have shown that patients gain health knowledge by using information (Kushniruk, 2019). This study agreed with these findings, given that when patients believe information received from healthcare providers, it can help patients adhere to health principles to save their lives and improve their health outcomes. Believing in information provided by health professionals can trigger optimal treatments, optimal management, expedited recovery, and an improved patient outcome (Kushniruk, 2019). Similar findings from a study by Nikolopoulou et al. (2023) indicate that "gaps in knowledge about hepatitis B and the transmission of infection, lack of awareness of their HBV serostatus, and concerns with safety and efficacy of hepatitis B vaccines, are still frequent among patients. This study agreed that patients can gain knowledge of prevention only when they are informed of the danger of exposure to HBV and HCV and the necessary steps for prevention.

More results show that the patients want to improve their health conditions. For example, another participant said: "*My motivating factor is that I want to improve my health condition*". The finding relates to a study by Bodenheimer (2005) focusing on helping patients suffering from chronic illness improve their health-related behaviours. It indicated that well-informed patients who participate in health-related decisions to improve their health conditions can have better health-related behaviours and clinical outcomes. This study agreed that information is crucial in improving the health conditions of patients suffering from chronic diseases and can help HBV and HCV patients improve their health conditions. Patients with improved health conditions have a lot to contribute to improving their country's social and economic status.

According to more results from the interview, a participant admitted that "*health information is essential to my health needs*". The most important motivating factor for using health information is when patients realise it is essential to their health needs. Similar findings from Ek and Heinstro (2011) indicated that various sources have been used to gather information for various purposes, such as to solve problems, given that such information can improve their health. Adebayo (2019:3) noted that individuals seek information for use and to achieve a goal. In another context, people living with HIV/AIDS (PLWHA) may interact with various information sources in order to use information to solve a pressing problem.

Based on research question two, patients were asked, *“based on your experiences of the diseases, how important is information related to your use of information?”*

Understanding the vital role of information is essential for patients' information use, mainly based on the patient's experiences during hospital visitations or treatment experiences. It is essential to note that health information provision by healthcare managers is essential to guide the effective management of healthcare services, such as preventing chronic diseases services in developed and developing countries worldwide, and such information should be availed to patients while visiting healthcare facilities (Batarseh *et al.*, 2020, p. 1). The responses from the participants indicate that using information is very important for improving their health, and some noted that *“using information is very important for them to stay informed”*. A similar study highlighted the importance of health information use and how information is essential to enhancing patients' health improvement and outcomes and can also improve the overall quality of patient care (Peyman *et al.*, 2012). The following were responses from most of the participants:

Using information is very important for improving my health, staying informed, and seeking better treatment.

To establish the relevance of health information, it is imperative to consider the goal of individuals using it and how important it is to their health needs. This is especially true when it comes to the effectiveness of health information in managing and eliminating chronic diseases such as HBV and HCV.

Based on research question three, the participants were asked: *Do you believe in the usefulness of hepatitis B and C-related health information?*

Findings revealed that most participants believed in the usefulness of hepatitis B and C-related health information provided at the hospital, which is why information for patients contributes to "improved quality of life for patients" (Sha & Abu-Amara, 2013). Information is an important "strategy used to improve people's knowledge regarding preventive methods, pain management, adherence to medications about chronic diseases such as HBV and HCV (If contacted), and cure" (Sha & Abu-Amara, 2013). Knowledge of HBV and HCV is crucial because it helps increase awareness. Moreover, education helps effect changes in attitude regarding health practices and improvement in individual HBV and HCV patients (Haq *et al.*, 2014, p. 807). Patient education helps patients understand the importance of adherence to treatment, the complications of non-adherence, and the

need for assistance with medicine and other care (Cacoub *et al.*, 2008, p. 6195). The participant's notes;

"I believe health information is useful for my health".

"Yes, I believe health information is useful for my health".

Raza *et al.* (2013) emphasised the importance of information in creating awareness about the risks related to chronic diseases such as HBV and HCV infection during counselling intervention. The study suggested that preventive strategies should be emphasised through information use through mass media, education, and counselling to control the spread of the diseases". Both patients and healthcare professionals have benefited immensely from patient education, primarily through digital sources or traditional formats (Kavarthapu & Sankari, 2017). Patient education can help improve knowledge and understanding of diseases or infections through HBV and HCV (Haq *et al.*, 2014). Patients' educational materials on HBV, HCV, cirrhosis, and hepatocellular carcinoma can be made available to effectively close the gap between the availability and utilisation of material resources (Gulati, 2016).

Conclusion

This current study exposed various factors motivating patients' information use, such as trust in the information provided, the need to gain health knowledge, improvement in health conditions, the belief in the information received, and the belief that health information is vital to health needs. To evaluate the danger of not getting treated and to use information to increase their chances of survival. This study ascertained the usefulness of hepatitis B and C health-related information. On the other hand, this study established that using health information by patients is very important for them to stay informed and seek better treatment. Furthermore, most patients believe that health information is helpful for their health.

Based on the findings in this study, the researchers agreed that health information is essential for the overall improvement of health conditions in any patient. It is vital that trust in the information received, especially from the caregivers, is established between patients and caregivers to facilitate mutual communication that can speed up speedy recovery and medication adherence. The utilisation of essential health information is vital to enable patients to evaluate the danger of not getting treated, and it is also important to

use information to increase their chances of survival. Patients accessing and using health-related information can increase their survival rate and improve their health conditions.

This study was the first to investigate the factors contributing to the use of Information by HBV and HCV patients at Ngwelezane Hospital, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. It also contributes to the literature establishing essential factors motivating patients' information use at Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa.

Recommendations

Based on findings from this study, the following are recommended for the patients:

1. Patients must be empowered with information to improve their health, primarily through their health professionals. It is equally important to consult healthcare professionals for personalised treatment advice.
2. While health information is beneficial for various health purposes, patients must avoid self-diagnosis using information received through unreliable sources. Patients must seek information from the right source to understand symptoms related to their conditions. Accurate information on diagnosis must be sought from healthcare professionals.
3. Patients must understand the importance of their health information, which could influence various factors beyond medical interventions, including diet, exercise, sleep, stress management, and social connections.

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Author Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate in this study were ensured. The researchers ensured that the research design adheres to ethical standards as enshrined by the research policy of the University of Zululand, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa (UZREC1711110-030PGD2020/8; dated 2/09/2020 and 2021, respectively). The ethical clearances were approved and provided by the committee of Ngwelezane District Hospital, KwaZulu-Natal Province, South Africa, and ethical clearance from the health research and knowledge management unit of the Department of Health, KwaZulu-Natal Province (NHRD REF.KZ-220-004; dated 13/11/2020), South Africa to ensure the compliance of the research practices to the ethical standard.